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Influence of Monitoring and Corruption on Budget Implementation in Akwa Ibom State

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Abstract

Budget implementation has remained a major governance challenge in Akwa Ibom State, with persistent concerns over the gap between budgetary provisions and actual performance. This study investigates the influence of monitoring and corruption on budget implementation in Akwa Ibom State. Anchored on the theory of prebendalism, the study explored how the level of monitoring affects the efficiency of budget execution and whether corruption significantly impedes the implementation process. A qualitative research design was adopted, drawing evidence from documentary sources and unstructured interviews with key stakeholders in the budgeting process. The findings revealed that inadequate monitoring mechanisms and weak oversight contribute substantially to poor budget implementation. The study also established that corruption undermines transparency and accountability, distorts resource allocation, and erodes public trust in the budgeting system. It was concluded that effective and transparent monitoring, coupled with strong anti-corruption measures, is critical to improving budget implementation outcomes in the state. The study recommended, among others, the strengthening of institutional monitoring frameworks, regular performance evaluation, and the establishment of a functional anti-corruption body to ensure fiscal discipline and accountability in budget execution.

Keywords: budget, corruption, monitoring, prebendalism, Akwa Ibom State

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1.1 Introduction

Since independence in 1960, successive governments in Nigeria have consistently engaged in the annual ritual of preparing and implementing budgets as a constitutional and administrative obligation. The budget, being a detailed statement of projected income and expenditure, serves as a key fiscal policy instrument for promoting growth, ensuring stability, and improving citizens' welfare. Despite progressive increases in budgetary allocations over the years, the realities of Nigeria's development trajectory reveal a persistent gap between budget formulation and actual implementation. This disconnect is reflected in the country's low Human Development Index (HDI) ranking, which stood at 0.514 in 2014 and 0.548 in 2024, placing Nigeria in the low human development category (UNDP, 2024).

The recurring problem of poor budget implementation has continued to weaken public confidence in governance. While budgets are designed to drive infrastructural development, enhance social welfare, and ensure equitable resource distribution, outcomes often fall short of projections. The discrepancy between approved budgets and tangible development outcomes has been attributed to a combination of administrative inefficiencies, poor monitoring mechanisms, and pervasive corruption across all tiers of government. In many cases, projects captured in the budgets are either poorly executed or completely abandoned, denying citizens the benefits of planned public investments.

In Akwa Ibom State, the issue of budget implementation mirrors the national challenge. Despite substantial allocations for capital projects, the execution of developmental programmes remains far below expectation. Reports from the International Centre for Investigative Reporting (2021) and the Akwa Ibom State Auditor-General's annual reports have raised concerns over questionable expenditures, inflated contracts, and discrepancies in project costs. For example, allegations of inflated procurement for official vehicles and aircraft maintenance underscore how corruption distorts the fiscal process and diverts public funds from their intended purposes. The Akwa Ibom Integrity Group further revealed that over 300 projects, including rural roads, classroom blocks, water schemes, and electrification projects, were abandoned at various stages of completion, a situation linked largely to inadequate oversight and corrupt practices.

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Effective budget implementation depends greatly on the efficiency of monitoring systems. Monitoring ensures that funds are disbursed according to plan, projects are executed within timelines, and outcomes align with policy objectives. In the absence of strong monitoring frameworks, budget execution becomes vulnerable to mismanagement, resource diversion, and political interference. Equally, corruption undermines fiscal discipline, compromises transparency, and erodes the credibility of public financial management systems. When public officials manipulate budgetary processes for personal or political gain, the result is often poor service delivery, uncompleted projects, and growing public disillusionment.

In Akwa Ibom State, these two factors of weak monitoring and entrenched corruption have emerged as critical obstacles to effective budget implementation. Their combined effect manifests in inflated project costs, ghost projects, poor accountability, and limited developmental impact despite large fiscal outlays. Consequently, examining how the level of monitoring affects budget implementation, and how corruption influences budget performance becomes essential for understanding the broader challenge of fiscal governance in the state.

This study therefore investigates the influence of monitoring and corruption on budget implementation in Akwa Ibom State, with the aim of identifying the extent to which these two factors contribute to poor execution outcomes and proposing measures to strengthen accountability, transparency, and fiscal efficiency in public administration.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Even though the 13 percent oil derivation fund brings in a lot of money for Akwa Ibom State, the lives of its people have not gotten much better. This makes people worry about how well the government carries out its budgets. The state always makes big promises in its budgets, but the projects and public services it provides are still not up to par. Contracts that are too high, projects that are never finished, and spending that is questionable all point to a lack of oversight and corruption in the budget process. Corruption makes it hard to hold people accountable and changes how resources are used. Poor monitoring lets people use funds for things they shouldn't and makes it hard to keep an eye on projects. As a result, there is a growing gap between how much money is spent and how much progress is made. This study aims to investigate the impact of monitoring levels on budget implementation and to assess the degree to which corruption hinders effective budget performance in Akwa Ibom State.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

While the general objective of the study is to examine major constraints to budget implementation in Akwa Ibom State, the specific objectives are:

- i. To examine how the level of monitoring affects budget implementation.
- ii. To ascertain if there is any relationship between corruption and budget implementation.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions were generated to guide the study:

- i. Does the level of monitoring affect budget implementation?
- ii. What is the relationship between corruption and budget implementation?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

- i. There is a significant relationship between monitoring and budget implementation in Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. There is a significant relationship between corruption and budget implementation in Akwa Ibom State.

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study is significant as it provides an in-depth analysis of two major factors undermining effective budget implementation in Akwa Ibom State: weak monitoring and corruption. Despite recurring budget cycles, the absence of rigorous monitoring mechanisms and the persistence of corrupt practices have continued to hinder the translation of budgetary plans into tangible development outcomes. By examining how monitoring influences budget performance and how corruption disrupts fiscal accountability, this study offers evidence-based insights that can guide policy reforms. The findings will be useful to the Akwa Ibom State government, legislators, and public finance managers in strengthening oversight systems, promoting transparency, and improving budgetary outcomes. Academics, civil society organisations, and financial institutions will also find the study valuable for advancing discussions and strategies aimed at enhancing good governance and effective public resource management.

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2.1 Literature Review

2.1.1 Concept of Budget and Budget Implementation

A budget represents a comprehensive financial plan that outlines a government's projected revenues and expenditures over a defined period, typically one fiscal year. It is both a financial and policy instrument designed to achieve developmental objectives through strategic allocation of resources (Khan & Jain, 2007). As a fiscal management tool, the budget ensures accountability, transparency, and economic stability when properly implemented.

Budget implementation refers to the execution of approved plans, translating appropriations into tangible outputs through effective disbursement and utilisation of funds by relevant ministries, departments, and agencies (MDAs). In Nigeria, implementation has consistently faced challenges, including delayed fund releases, weak monitoring, corruption, and political interference (Adekoya, 2012; Ekeocha, 2012). Effective implementation remains the critical stage that determines whether budgetary intentions are transformed into developmental outcomes.

2.1.2 Budget Monitoring and Evaluation

Monitoring and evaluation (M&E) are essential instruments for achieving accountability and efficiency in public budgeting. According to Slukhai (2011), monitoring provides continuous assessment of financial activities and outcomes against planned targets, while evaluation involves systematic appraisal of relevance, effectiveness, and sustainability of budgeted programmes.

Performance-based budgeting models emphasise results-orientated implementation rather than mere expenditure compliance (Siyanbola, 2013). Likalama and Nyangau (2017) note that consistent monitoring enables timely adjustments in spending to align with goals, ensuring optimal resource utilisation. Egbunike and Anamma (2017) further assert that periodic comparison between actual expenditure and budgeted estimates promotes fiscal discipline and transparency.

However, in Nigeria, weak monitoring frameworks and poor data systems have undermined the effectiveness of M&E. Oversight agencies often lack the capacity or independence to enforce compliance, leading to low accountability and wastage of resources. The absence of rigorous follow-up on capital projects results in incomplete or abandoned projects, which distorts fiscal performance and diminishes public trust.

2.1.3 Corruption and Budget Implementation

Corruption is defined as the abuse of public office for private gain (Transparency International, 2020). It remains a major impediment to good governance and effective budget execution. It distorts resource allocation, inflates contract costs, and reduces the quality of public services (Rose-Ackerman & Palifka, 2016; Gans-Morse et al., 2018).

In Nigeria, corruption has become institutionalised across all levels of government, manifesting in forms such as embezzlement, contract inflation, bribery, and diversion of funds (Akindele, 2005; Kayode, 2013). Large-scale fraud, as evidenced by the fuel subsidy and pension fund scandals, exemplifies the misuse of public funds that could have enhanced infrastructure and social services (Kolawole, 2013).

Corruption undermines budget implementation by distorting priorities, discouraging monitoring efforts, and eroding the credibility of public institutions. The resultant inefficiency contributes to persistent development deficits and public disillusionment. Rose-Ackerman and Palifka (2016) emphasise that corruption not only weakens governance structures but also limits citizen participation and oversight.

The reviewed literature demonstrates that effective budget implementation depends largely on two interrelated factors: strong monitoring mechanisms and reduced corruption. Monitoring ensures accountability and timely project execution, while corruption undermines the integrity and impact of fiscal decisions. Although several studies have examined budget performance in Nigeria, limited attention has been paid to the specific interaction between these two variables at the state level. This study therefore seeks to fill that gap by empirically examining how monitoring and corruption influence budget implementation in Akwa Ibom State.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study adopts the prebendalism theory as its theoretical underpinning. The theory, rooted in the Nigerian context, explains how political officeholders perceive public resources as personal entitlements, distributing them among clients and supporters (Joseph, 1987). This patronage-driven behaviour fosters corruption and undermines transparent governance. Within the context of budget implementation, prebendal practices distort monitoring processes and prioritise political gains over developmental outcomes.

2.3 Review of Empirical Literature

Several studies have examined the links between budget monitoring, corruption, and implementation in Nigeria. Ianna (2018) analysed budget implementation and governance and observed that weak governance often leads to poor execution, where outcomes fail to reach intended beneficiaries. The study recommended wider stakeholder participation during budget formulation to strengthen ownership and accountability.

Similarly, Nwaorgu (2018) examined how individual dominance and political manipulation distort the budget process, concluding that transparency and accountability reforms are vital for effective implementation. Nwala and Ogboji (2020) assessed the impact of budget implementation on Nigeria's economic growth (1981–2018) and found that capital expenditure positively influenced GDP, while recurrent expenditure had a negative effect, largely due to poor monitoring and disregard for due process.

At the subnational level, Uyime-Abasi et al. (2021) identified unethical practices, inadequate motivation, and low transparency as key barriers to effective housing budgeting in Akwa Ibom State. They proposed adopting the Medium-Term Expenditure Framework (MTEF) and enhancing monitoring mechanisms. Likewise, Nnamseh and Akpan (2021) linked abandoned infrastructure projects in the state to weak oversight, corruption, and poor implementation practices.

Further, Namso and Akpan (2022) examined the performance of small and medium-scale enterprises (SMSEs) in Akwa Ibom State and found that most policy failures stem from inadequate monitoring and corrupt practices. Joseph and Ataire (2022) also reported that the lack of transparency in the state's budget process undermines accountability and democratic governance. In an earlier study, Udoh (2013) found a weak relationship between budgeted and actual capital expenditures in coastal local governments, attributing this to fiscal indiscipline and poor monitoring.

These studies reveal that ineffective monitoring, political interference, and corruption are central challenges to budget implementation in Nigeria. Strengthening institutional accountability, promoting transparency, and enforcing anti-corruption measures are essential for improving budget performance in Akwa Ibom State.

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3. Methodology

This study employed a qualitative design using documentary analysis complemented by key informant interviews to explore how monitoring and corruption influence budget implementation in Akwa Ibom State. The state, located in Nigeria's South-South region, comprises 31 local government areas and a population of over five million. Primary data were obtained through purposive interviews with senior officials in the Ministry of Finance and the Budget Office, while secondary data came from scholarly journals, books, policy reports, and credible online sources. Data were analysed using descriptive-contextual and discursive techniques to identify emerging themes and ensure credibility. Ethical standards were strictly upheld: informed consent was obtained, participants' confidentiality maintained, and data integrity preserved. The study avoided all forms of falsification or misuse and complied with copyright and environmental responsibility principles.

4 Data Presentation and Analysis

4.1 The Effect of monitoring on budget implementation in Akwa Ibom State?

To assess whether monitoring influences budget implementation, five key informants from the Akwa Ibom State Ministry of Finance and Budget Office were interviewed. Their responses are shown in table 1 below:

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Table 1: Perceptions of Key Informants on the Effect of Monitoring on Budget Implementation in Akwa Ibom State

Participant	Key Point(s) Highlighted	Implications for Budget Implementation
Participant 1	Regular and frequent monitoring enhances accountability and ensures adherence to financial guidelines.	Promotes transparency and efficient use of funds.
Participant 2	Continuous review of expenditure ensures funds are used in line with approved budgets and reduces misappropriation.	Strengthens public trust and accountability.
Participant 3	Regular oversight enables early detection of financial irregularities and deviations from budget plans.	Prevents crises and ensures timely corrective action.
Participant 4	Data-driven monitoring provides insight into financial performance, supporting better decision-making.	Optimises resource allocation and strategic adjustments.
Participant 5	High-quality monitoring improves compliance with budgetary regulations through detailed assessment and evaluation.	Ensures budgetary processes align with financial standards.

Source: Field Survey (2024)

The responses from the table shows that both the frequency and quality of monitoring play a critical role in ensuring transparency, accountability, and effective resource utilisation. This therefore means that the level and quality of monitoring significantly influence the success of budget implementation in Akwa Ibom State. Frequent, transparent, and data-driven monitoring enhances accountability, prevents irregularities, and ensures resources are efficiently utilised. This finding supports the hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between monitoring and budget implementation.

4.2 Corruption and Budget Implementation in Akwa Ibom State?

To assess how corruption influences budget implementation, eight key informants provided detailed insights into how corrupt practices distort fund allocation, inflate project costs, and compromise project quality in Akwa Ibom State. Their responses are revealed in table 2 below.

Table 2: Perceptions of Key Informants on the Effect of Corruption on Budget Implementation in Akwa Ibom State

Participant	Key Points Highlighted	Implications for Budget Implementation
1	Corruption skews allocation of funds towards self-serving projects rather than public needs.	Leads to misallocation of resources and underperformance of critical projects.
2	Procurement manipulation inflates project costs and encourages substandard work.	Reduces efficiency and wastes public funds.
3	Funds are diverted to politically motivated or personal-interest projects.	Causes uneven development and neglect of essential sectors.
4	Favouritism in fund allocation prioritises connected individuals over capable contractors.	Reduces project quality and fairness in resource distribution.
5	Lack of transparency and accountability enables diversion to phantom or unverified projects.	Weakens public financial management and increases misuse of funds.
6	Misappropriation of funds compromises project quality and completion.	Results in poorly executed or abandoned projects.
7	Short-term, politically driven projects are prioritised over sustainable initiatives.	Encourages superficial development and poor long-term outcomes.
8	Corruption fosters dependency and entitlement among political elites.	Perpetuates systemic corruption and undermines institutional integrity.

Source: Field Survey (2024)

The responses in table 2 reveal that corruption not only misdirects resources but also undermines transparency, fairness, and efficiency in public spending. The evidence suggests a strong and negative relationship between corruption and effective budget implementation in Akwa Ibom State. Corruption distorts resource allocation, inflates costs, and compromises project outcomes, ultimately eroding public trust and diminishing the developmental impact of government spending. These findings support the hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between corruption and budget implementation.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

4.3.1 Level of Monitoring and Budget Implementation

The findings of this study revealed a significant relationship between compromised budget monitoring and poor budget implementation in Akwa Ibom State. This supports the position of Ekhatior and Chima (2015), who observed that many public policies in Nigeria fail due to persistent weaknesses in budget formulation and implementation. Critical among these weaknesses are delayed budget preparation, late submission and appropriation, poor implementation planning, and compromised monitoring mechanisms. Similarly, Ugoh and Ukpere (2009) noted that although annual budgets are intended to provide expenditure estimates for infrastructure and social development, such as roads, electricity, healthcare, and agriculture, their implementation has often been undermined by structural and procedural inefficiencies.

The current study also found that the state's monitoring mechanisms fail to effectively prevent the misuse and diversion of funds. Weak oversight has created opportunities for financial leakages and mismanagement. This corroborates Folscher's (2007) argument that ineffective monitoring and evaluation deepen the consequences of poor implementation, delay institutional responses, and reduce the timeliness of corrective action when irregularities are detected.

Furthermore, Udoh (2013) emphasised that effective budget monitoring requires analytical, problem-solving, and communication skills. Monitoring teams that lack these competencies are unlikely to interpret financial data accurately or ensure accountability. This aligns with the study's finding that the absence of skilled and dedicated monitoring personnel contributes significantly to poor budget outcomes in Akwa Ibom State.

In summary, the study demonstrates that effective budget monitoring is central to improving implementation performance. Strengthening oversight capacity, enhancing technical competence, and enforcing transparency in monitoring processes are critical to achieving better fiscal governance and accountability outcomes.

4.3.2 Relationship Between Corruption and Budget Implementation

The findings from the interviews indicate that corruption significantly hampers effective budget implementation in Akwa Ibom State. Participants consistently linked corruption to fund misallocation, inflated project costs, poor-quality outcomes, and uneven development. These findings corroborate earlier studies that have emphasised corruption as a central barrier to fiscal accountability and policy effectiveness in Nigeria.

Ekhaton and Chima (2015) observed that the efficacy of the budget as an instrument for achieving public policy objectives depends on transparent planning and allocation of funds devoid of corrupt intentions. Similarly, Plebn (2009) argued that budgeting encompasses a cyclical process involving preparation, authorisation, implementation, accounting, and auditing, all of which can be undermined by corruption if integrity mechanisms are weak. When these processes are manipulated, budget implementation becomes ineffective, leading to financial leakages and unmet policy goals.

Olaoye (2014) further noted that budgetary allocations in Nigeria often suffer from the negative influence of corruption and negligence by public officers, rendering the national budget incapable of achieving its intended developmental outcomes. The manipulation of fiscal processes by political elites and bureaucrats distorts expenditure priorities and weakens institutional capacity. This aligns with the interview data, which revealed that favouritism, diversion of funds, and lack of transparency are recurring issues within Akwa Ibom State's budgeting process.

In a related argument, Ekeocha (2012) highlighted inefficiencies in fiscal decision-making within Nigeria's public sector, noting the prevalence of internal disputes over inflated project costs and misappropriated spending. Practices such as inserting non-essential projects, legislative bargaining, and inadequate scrutiny of appropriations further weaken the credibility of the budgeting process. These systemic weaknesses, echoed in the participants' responses, foster corruption and erode public trust in fiscal governance.

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Egiyi and Nwadiolor (2020) proposed that mitigating corruption in budget implementation requires citizen sensitisation on budgeting processes and the establishment of proactive mechanisms for oversight and accountability. They emphasised the need for strengthened checks and balances across the executive and legislative arms to ensure fiscal discipline and prevent boundary overreach. This recommendation aligns with the present study's findings, which underscore the necessity of transparent monitoring, active stakeholder involvement, and institutional reform to curtail corruption and enhance budget performance.

In summary, both the empirical findings and the literature affirm that corruption exerts a substantial negative influence on budget implementation in Akwa Ibom State. The evidence points to the urgent need for stronger governance frameworks, capacity building, and participatory fiscal management to improve accountability and ensure that public resources are efficiently utilised for development.

5.1 Conclusion

This study examined how budget monitoring and corruption influence budget implementation in Akwa Ibom State. The findings revealed that compromised monitoring systems and entrenched corruption significantly hinder effective budget performance. Weak oversight, limited technical capacity among monitoring teams, and slow institutional responses to irregularities have contributed to persistent implementation failures. These weaknesses have resulted in the diversion of public funds, poor execution of capital projects, and limited service delivery outcomes.

The study further established that effective budget monitoring requires more than procedural compliance; it demands analytical competence, transparency, and accountability at every stage of the budget cycle. Likewise, curbing corruption within the budgetary process calls for strong political will, timely audits, and active citizen participation.

In light of these findings, it is concluded that improving budget implementation in Akwa Ibom State depends largely on strengthening monitoring frameworks, enhancing capacity building for budget officers, and enforcing anti-corruption measures. A more transparent, participatory, and accountable budget process will not only ensure the efficient use of public resources but also promote sustainable socioeconomic development in the state.

5.1 Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are made in alignment with the two research objectives:

- 1. Strengthen Monitoring Mechanisms:** The government should institutionalise continuous and independent budget monitoring processes involving professionals with proven analytical and financial management skills. Establishing clear monitoring frameworks will ensure that budget implementation aligns with planned objectives and that deviations are promptly corrected.
- 2. Capacity Building for Budget Personnel:** Regular training and retraining programmes should be organised for budget officers and monitoring committees to enhance technical competence, data analysis, communication, and ethical standards. A well-trained team will improve the accuracy and timeliness of monitoring reports, leading to better implementation outcomes.
- 3. Enhance Transparency and Accountability:** All monitoring and reporting processes should be made open to public scrutiny through digital platforms, quarterly reports, and legislative oversight. This transparency will minimise manipulation of data and foster greater public confidence in government spending.
- 4. Enforce Anti-Corruption Frameworks:** Anti-corruption agencies should be empowered to investigate, prosecute, and sanction all forms of financial misconduct in budget execution without political interference. Strengthening these mechanisms will deter corrupt practices and promote fiscal discipline.
- 5. Promote Citizen Participation:** Civil society organisations, the media, and local communities should be encouraged to actively participate in monitoring public projects and budgetary allocations. Their involvement will serve as an additional accountability layer, reducing opportunities for corruption and ensuring that allocated funds are used for their intended purposes.

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